

THE HIVOCOMP PROJECT: CARBON FIBRE/PA12 HYBRID SINGLE POLYMER COMPOSITES

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Introduction

Traditional carbon fibre composites deliver exceptional stiffness and strength but can often have a limited extensibility and poor damage tolerance especially at lower operating temperatures. On the other hand, the development of single polymer composites over the last 20 years has seen the emergence of a new material that is lightweight and has exceptional toughness even at low temperatures. A goal of the new FP7 project, HIVOCOMP (www.hivocomp.eu) is to combine the best attributes of these two material types by creating a self-reinforced, single polymer/carbon fibre hybrid. The aim is to produce a composite material that has enhanced stiffness over a pure single polymer composite sheet without sacrificing the excellent toughness and ductility usually shown by these materials.

While the concept of combining a high stiffness, but brittle, fibre with a ductile polymeric fibre with a much larger strain to failure is not new, the production of hybridised self reinforced polymer composites is very much a new research area. All of these studies (for example the work at the KU Leuven [1, 2]) have looked at combining discrete layers of a prepreg composite and a self reinforced polymer (SRP) sheet. While there are a number of published methods for producing self reinforced polymer composites (for example film stacking, powder impregnation and bicomponent tapes), the one used for this research is hot compaction, which was developed and patented at the University of Leeds [3-5]. The underlying principle is to take assemblies of oriented polymer fibres or tapes, and expose them to a critical temperature, while held under pressure, such that a thin skin on the surface of each oriented element is 'selectively melted'. On subsequent fast cooling, the melted material recrystallizes to form the matrix phase of a self reinforced polymer composite, with the remaining fraction of the original oriented phase acting as the

reinforcement. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the process. The virtues of this technique are that the matrix phase is produced around each fibre, negating the need for infiltration, and that molecular continuity is achieved between the two components of the final composite. Research has shown this to work with a wide range of oriented thermoplastic fibres and tapes including polyethylene [6], polypropylene [7], polyester [8] and nylon 6.6 [9].

Figure 1: A schematic of the hot compaction process for oriented polymer fibres. The oriented phase is shown in blue and the melted and recrystallised matrix phase in red.

In a previous study, [1], the effect of combining individual layers of a prepreg composite and a single polymer composite were studied. In this paper we have taken this concept further by carrying out the hybridisation within each yarn, which we term intra-yarn hybridisation.

In this technique oriented PA12 fibres and carbon fibres are co-mingled to produce a hybridised fibre tow, which is then woven or braided into a cloth using standard textile techniques. Once the cloth has been woven, it is processed using the hot compaction technique to produce a consolidated hybrid composite.

Figure 2: A schematic of the hot compaction process for co-mingled carbon (●) and oriented polymer fibres (●)

The difference in using the hot compaction process for a mixture of carbon and polymer fibres is that there are now less polymer fibres to produce the matrix phase (red), as shown schematically in Figure 2. Experiments have therefore been carried out to establish whether a homogenous composite can be

produced using such a co-mingled yarn, and whether this depends on either the fraction of carbon fibres, the arrangement of the fibres (UD, woven etc) or both.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The co-mingled yarns (T700 carbon fibres and oriented PA12 filaments) for this study were produced by Schappe Techniques, France using their patented stretch breaking technology. These were supplied in two combinations, a first batch with nominally 25% volume fraction of carbon fibres and then a second with a reduced fraction of nominally 13% volume fraction of carbon fibres. Microscopy of the combined tows showed that the mingling of the two components was excellent.

2.2 Production of composite samples

2.2.1 Hot compaction trials

Composite samples were produced using the Leeds hot compaction process [4]. The aim of this procedure is to establish a critical temperature at which a fraction of the oriented PA12 fibres are selectively melted, which then forms the matrix of the resulting composite. In this study samples were made from a range of fibre arrangements to assess how this would affect the critical temperature and resulting mechanical properties. A typical process is as follows. The oriented assembly is placed between soft aluminium sheets, two layers of silicon rubber to even out the pressure distribution, and then outer sheets of 2mm thick brass sheets. A thermocouple is placed in the centre of the assembly, and this is used for monitoring the temperature throughout the process. The assembly is then placed into a compression press set at the required temperature. A pressure of 5MPa is immediately applied and temperature monitoring is started. Once the temperature reaches the required temperature, it is left for 2 minutes. The whole press is then rapidly cooled to 50°C (using circulated water cooling) at which point the sample is removed from the press. The whole process takes around 7 minutes.

A typical processing schedule is shown in Figure 3. The dotted blue lines show the time at which the temperature reached the target value of 175°C and then the start of the fast cooling, 120 seconds (2 minutes) later.

2.2.2 Fibre arrangement

First, samples were made in a UD configuration by winding around a metal frame. Second, the co-mingled fibres were braided into a cloth using the facilities at Munich.

The Herzog braiding machine (RF-128-100) uses a 128 bobbin set-up which can produce a tubular cloth with braiding angles between 30 and 60°. The 25% carbon fibre tows were 2mm in diameter and could be successfully braided at an angle of +/- 45°. Various tubular diameters were braided, the most successful being 60mm. Once braided, the tubular cloth was cut to provide layers of cloth for hot compaction trials. The style of braiding was biaxial.

The 13% carbon fibre tow was of a smaller diameter (~1mm) and so the maximum diameter that could be braided, without gaps, was slightly lower at 50mm.

2.3 Testing

Both tensile and bending tests were carried out on the hybrid composite samples. These were carried out in accordance with ASTM D3039 (tensile) and ASTM D6272 (bending).

The tensile test samples were 10mm wide and 150mm long. The gauge length was set to 65mm and the sample strain was measured in the centre 15mm using a Messphysik video-extensometer. The testing speed was 5mm/min, giving a nominal strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} . Tests were carried out at 20°C and 50% RH. Samples were left to equilibrate at these conditions for 5 days before testing.

The bending test samples were 10mm wide and 70mm long. Modulus measurements were made using a span/thickness ratio of 25:1 while stress-strain curves to break were made using a span/thickness ratio of 16:1 as recommended by the standard. The testing speed was 5mm/min, giving the same strain rate as for the tensile tests of 10^{-3} s^{-1} . Tests were carried out at 20°C and 50% RH. Samples were left to equilibrate at these conditions for 5 days before testing.

Wide angle x-ray scattering (WAXS) pictures and scans were taken from the various samples to follow the loss of molecular orientation over the critical hot compaction temperature range.

2.4 Measurement of the carbon fibre fraction

The fraction of carbon fibres in the two co-mingled tows was measured using the burn off test (ASTM

D2584). Samples were heated in a porcelain crucible until the PA12 matrix ignited. The samples are then placed into a furnace set at 450°C and left for 4 hours to remove the carbonaceous residue. A measurement of the weight before and after the burn off allowed the weight fraction to be calculated. This fraction is converted into the carbon fibre volume fraction by assuming a density of respectively 1015 kg/m³ and 1800 kg/m³ for PA12 and CF. These results gave a volume fraction of 25% and 13% for the two tows supplied by Schappe.

3 Results

3.1 UD samples – 25% carbon fibre tows - tension

UD samples from the 25% carbon fibre tows were made over the temperature range of 171°C to 179°C (as suggested by DSC measurements) plus an additional sample made at 190°C to completely melt the PA12 fibres. Tensile tests were carried out in both the fibre direction and the transverse direction, for samples made over this temperature range and the results are shown in Figure 6.

In the fibre direction (Figure 6a) the results were seen to be almost independent of the hot compaction temperature, being dominated by the carbon fibres. Conversely, in the transverse direction (Figure 6b) the strength was very dependent on the hot compaction temperature (i.e. the amount of selectively produced matrix phase), reaching a maximum at around 178°C.

An important aspect of the hot compaction process is to be able to establish a temperature where good bonding can be achieved without substantial loss of molecular orientation of the oriented components. WAXS photographs and scans were carried out on the compacted samples to investigate this aspect.

Circumferential scans were carried out with the x-ray diffractometer set a value of 2θ of 5.8°. This is the first meridional peak, characteristic of the crystalline structure of the oriented PA12 fibres. It is shown by the white arrow on Figure 7. Monitoring this either qualitatively, by taking photos (Figure 7) or by quantitative scans (Figure 8) show that the oriented molecular orientation structure is lost at around 179°C. These results suggest a safe compaction temperature of ~176°C, indicated by the dotted red line on Figure 6b.

3.2 UD samples – 25% carbon fibre tows - bending

In the next set of experiments, bending tests were carried out on a range of samples in the fibre direction. As with the longitudinal tensile tests, the results were reasonably independent of the compaction temperature. However, there were two very important differences to the tensile tests. First, as seen from a representative sample shown in Figure 9 and made at 173°C, the sample failed in a ductile manner, compared to the brittle behavior seen in tension. Catastrophic failure of the sample did not occur when the carbon fibres broke on the tension side of the sample. The compressive side of the sample continued to bear load to around 8% strain.

Second, and perhaps even more interestingly, if the PA12 filaments were completely melted (by processing at temperature of 190°C), then the sample reverted to brittle failure in bending. This shows the benefit of retaining molecular orientation in the sample, by establishing an optimum temperature in the melting range of the PA12 fibres.

3.3 Braided samples – 25% carbon fibre tows

The next series of tests were carried out using the braided cloth, manufactured over the same temperature range. Figure 10 shows typical tensile results from these samples.

The results showed that for this braided cloth, and for the 25% carbon fibre tows, a homogeneously bonded sample could not be made at 176°C. A temperature of 178°C was required to produce enough of the melted and recrystallised matrix phase for good consolidation. However, this is considered too close to the temperature where substantial melting, and loss of molecular orientation, occurs (Figure 8), suggesting that a commercially realistic processing window is not achievable with braided (or woven) 25% carbon fibre co-mingled tows (unless in a tightly packed UD configuration).

3.4 UD and Braided samples – 13% carbon fibre tows

3.4.1 UD samples

The results from the 25% carbon fibre tows suggest that applying the hot compaction technique produced interesting mechanical properties, but only

in a very narrow temperature window. In order to give a more usable processing window, a second set of experiments were carried out using 13% carbon fibre co-mingled tows. Figure 11 shows the results from the 13% volume fraction co-mingled tows in comparison with those shown previously for the 25% carbon fibre tows.

In the fibre direction the properties were once again, almost independent of the compaction temperature. The results shown in Figure 11a compare the tensile behavior of the 25% and 13% fraction tows, at the same compaction temperature of 173°C. The stiffness and strength, for the 13% fraction of carbon fibres, were, as expected, approximately a half of that for the 25% fraction.

In the transverse direction the results were even more interesting (Figure 11b). It was found that the transverse strength, at a comparable compaction temperature, was significantly higher for the lower fraction of carbon fibres, due, presumably, to the greater proportion of the melted and recrystallised matrix material produced. This has the effect of widening the effective processing window, as a lower compaction temperature can be used, thereby giving a greater distance away from the temperature at which substantial crystalline melting occurs (178°C).

3.4.2 Braided samples

The 13% carbon fibre tows were again braided at Munich. Samples were compacted first using a temperature of 175°C, suggested by the UD tests. Figure 12 shows tensile results for this sample compared to that made previously with the 25% co-mingled tows, also at 175°C.

The results shown in Figure 12 indicate that for the braided cloth using the 13% carbon fibre fraction co-mingled tows, a well bonded sample can be made at a lower temperature (175°C) than for the 25% tows tested previously, which required a temperature of 178°C to produce a homogeneous sample. Although the sample had an expected lower modulus, the tensile stress-strain curve was more linear leading to a comparable strength. This could be due to the better homogeneity as a result of an increased proportion of the matrix phase, but also due to lower crimp from this smaller diameter tow.

As discussed previously, the importance of this result is that this gives a usable temperature processing window, where a well consolidated sample can be made at 175°C, while retaining a substantial fraction of the oriented PA12 fibres.

Bending tests were next carried out, again comparing the behavior of the 25% and 13% carbon fibre fraction tows. The bending results (Figure 13) reflect those seen in tension. The 13% sample showed a lower modulus, and slightly lower strength. However the ductility of the 13% sample was improved compared to the 25% carbon fibre fraction. The results confirm that a carbon fibre fraction of 13% is a good compromise, delivering increased stiffness and strength over a pure PA12 self reinforced polymer composite, while still giving an adequate proportion of the melted fraction from the oriented PA12 fibres to enable consolidation using the hot compaction technique. Ductility is also seen in bending.

The following are considered to be the optimum processing conditions for the 13% co-mingled tows, while Table 1 shows a summary of typical mechanical properties of this optimum sample made at 175°C.

Hot compaction temperature	175°C
Compaction pressure	5 MPa
Dwell time at temperature	2 mins
Cooling	Fast cooling by circulated water

Co-mingled PA12 carbon fibres 0/90 properties – braided cloth Carbon fibre fraction 13%	
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	11.5
Tensile Strength (MPa)	120
Strain to failure (%)	1.6
Bending Modulus (GPa)	9.5
Bending Strength (MPa)	185
Strain to failure (%)	12

Table 1: Properties of compacted braided cloth (13%).

4. Conclusions

Experiments have shown that the optimum temperature required for production of hybrid composites using the hot compaction technique depends on both the arrangement of the hybrid tows and the carbon fibre fraction. For 25% volume fraction of carbon fibres, a well consolidated sample could be made at a temperature of 176°C, 2°C below the temperature at which major crystalline melting of the oriented PA12 fibres, and loss of molecular orientation, occurs. For braided cloth made from the same co-mingled tows, a higher temperature of 178°C was required to give a well consolidated sample, which is too close to the critical temperature.

Reducing the volume fraction of carbon fibres to 13%, gave a better result. Here, it was found that a well consolidated sample could be made from braided cloth using a lower temperature of 175°C. At this temperature, sufficient melted and recrystallised matrix material was produced to consolidate the structure and produce a homogeneous composite. This temperature was 3°C below the temperature at which substantial crystalline melting occurred, giving a usable temperature processing window.

In tension the samples were found to fail in a brittle manner, with the whole sample breaking on failure of the carbon fibres. Importantly, the hybrid samples were found to show ductile behaviour in bending as long as a substantial proportion of the molecular orientation of the PA12 fibres was retained. If the PA12 were completely melted, then the sample reverted to brittle behaviour.

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Figure 3: A typical process schedule

Figure 4: Braided cloth from 25% carbon fibre tows

Figure 5: Braided cloth from 13% carbon fibre tow

Figure 6a: UD results: fibre direction – 25% volume fraction of carbon fibres.

Figure 6b: UD results: transverse direction – 25% volume fraction of carbon fibres.

Figure 7: WAXS pictures of compacted samples.

Figure 9: Bending tests (fibre direction) for a sample compacted in the melting range of the fibre and a completely melted sample (made at 190°C).

Figure 8: Circumferential scans of compacted samples

Figure 10: Tensile tests on braided samples – 25% carbon fibre fraction samples

Figure 11a: UD tests – fibre direction – compare 25% and 13% carbon fibre fraction

Figure 11b: UD tests – transverse direction – compare 25% and 13% carbon fibre fraction

Figure 12: A comparison of tensile test results for the 25% and 13% carbon co-mingled tows: braided cloth

Figure 13: A comparison of the bending test results for the 25% and 13% carbon co-mingled tows: braided cloth

6. References

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